

EFFECTS OF MICROWAVE RESIN PREHEATING ON THE QUALITY OF RTM LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: An in-line microwave resin preheating system has been used to reduce the RTM cycle significantly. Microwave preheating lowers the resin viscosity during injection and modifies the thermal “age” of the resin, potentially influencing the quality of RTM laminates. Tensile properties of RTM laminates were measured with regard to improved fibre wet-out by the lower viscosity resin. Microwave resin preheating had an insignificant effect on the tensile modulus and strength of the laminates. Degree of cure measurements established that microwave resin preheating does not alter resin conversion within the laminate significantly. Localised pressure that develops within the mould during the cure phase can lead to mould deflections. Variations in the laminate thickness associated with these deflections are presented, and the use of microwave resin preheating to reduce these variations is discussed.

KEYWORDS: microwave heating, resin preheating, injection temperature profiling, thermal quench, resin transfer moulding, RTM, cycle time, laminate tensile properties

INTRODUCTION

Widespread acceptance of resin transfer moulding (RTM) within the high volume manufacturing sector has been inhibited by excessive production cycles. RTM comprises a fibre preforming stage, followed by resin injection into the preform with subsequent curing. Methods to accelerate the preforming stage are ongoing [1], with parallel research efforts being directed towards reductions in the moulding cycle time [2]. Thermal quench occurring when ambient temperature resin is injected into a heated mould has been identified as a principal cause of extended cycle times. Additional time is required to heat the mould and laminate to the resin initiation temperature, permitting the curing process to begin. The processing delays caused by thermal quench are compounded by lightweight shell tooling, having rapid thermal response characteristics. Previous work has demonstrated that thermal quench, and consequently, the cycle time can be reduced significantly by preheating the resin prior to injection [3]. An in-line microwave resin preheating system has been developed for this purpose at the University of Nottingham. The effect of microwave resin preheating on RTM laminates is addressed in this paper. Preheating alters the viscosity and thermal “age” of thermosetting resins. A lower resin viscosity was expected to improve fibre wet-out, increasing the mechanical properties of the laminate. Furthermore, altering the thermal age of the resin was anticipated to affect the degree of resin cure. In addition, microwave resin preheating can reduce the pressure that develops near

the injection gate during the cure phase. As a result, mould deflections and laminate thickness variations were expected to be reduced.

IN-LINE MICROWAVE RESIN PREHEATING FOR RTM

A rapid temperature drop (thermal quench) occurs near the injection gate as cool resin contacts the hot mould surface. This region remains quenched until the end of injection at which time heat is recovered gradually and the resin activation temperature is reached. Resin cures last at the injection gate, dictating the cycle time, as a result of thermal quench and a comparatively short residence time within the mould. One means of reducing thermal quench is to preheat the resin prior to injection. More rapid curing occurs since the heat required to initiate cure is decreased, resulting from a decreased temperature differential between the resin and the mould. Furthermore, the resin viscosity is lowered by preheating, facilitating flow through the mould and fibre reinforcement. Consequently, both impregnation and cycle times can be reduced.

Rapid heating of low thermal conductivity polymers (typically 0.3 W/mK [4]) is difficult to accomplish using standard conduction heating methods. A large thermal gradient between the heat transfer surface and the resin core is likely develop, inducing premature cure of reactive thermosetting resin systems. Unlike conduction heating, microwave heating is primarily volumetric, providing an even temperature distribution throughout the material. Rapid heat up rates and fast response times resulting from the low thermal capacity of the resin are possible due to the high power densities achievable using microwaves. The power density (P) within a dielectric material exposed to a microwave field can be expressed as:

$$P = 2\pi f E^2 \epsilon_0 \epsilon'' \quad (1)$$

where f is the microwave frequency (2.45 GHz), and ϵ_0 is the dielectric permittivity of free space. Equation 1 indicates that the power density within the material is a function of the electric field squared (E) and the dielectric loss factor (ϵ'') rather than the thermal properties of the material.

The effects of microwave processing on laminate properties is disputed. Research in this area has been confined to microwave curing, as opposed to microwave preheating. Yue and Boey [5] measured a 50% increase in the tensile modulus of epoxy cured using microwaves as opposed to conduction heating. Marand et al.[6] concluded that microwave processing led to a lower degree of cure and was expected to result in inferior mechanical properties. Lewis and Shaw [7] attempted to reconcile these contradictory findings by suggesting that the cure reaction rate is altered by microwave processing. Resins that contain a great number of microwave absorbing functional groups could produce a highly crosslinked laminate by microwave curing. These same reactive functional groups would not be affected by conventional conduction heating.

THE EXPERIMENTAL RTM FACILITY

Figure 1 is a schematic of the in-line microwave resin preheating system installed within the experimental RTM facility at the University of Nottingham. Prototype automotive undershield components were produced within a lightweight nickel shell mould. The undershield protects the engine and transmission assembly from heavy impact damage under rally conditions. The mould was instrumented with thermocouples and pressure transducers for process control. Hot oil heating was used to maintain a stable mould temperature. A constant pressure injection system consisting of a 30 litre resin storage vessel (maximum pressure of 7 bar) was used. Precatalysed resin was delivered to a centrally located pin gate in the lower mould half via the microwave

preheater. The distance between the microwave outlet and the injection gate was limited to 380 mm to minimise heat losses within the preheated resin before entering the mould. Resin flowed through the mould to two peripheral vents, expelling air in the process.

The microwave resin preheating system was operated within the automatic RTM cycle. A digital to analogue (DAC) board was installed within the personal computer (PC), and was linked, in turn, to a programmable logic controller (PLC). A digital switching facility on the card turned the power ON and OFF at appropriate times during the moulding sequence. Microwave power was adjusted through an analogue channel on the board via a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller. A feedback control loop based on the resin temperature at the microwave outlet and incorporating the PID power controller enabled a user defined resin temperature to be maintained during injection. A load cell on the resin storage vessel was used to monitor the amount of resin that entered the mould.

RTM CYCLE EFFECTS DUE TO IN-LINE MICROWAVE RESIN PREHEATING

Use of the in-line microwave system allowed resin to be heated at either a constant temperature during injection or according to a prescribed heating profile. Cycle time reductions of 26% have been demonstrated using constant temperature resin injection, however, this approach does not permit cycle time optimisation. Profiled resin preheating allowed the cure sequence to be controlled, minimising the cycle time, and limiting the in-mould pressure during cure [8].

A series of mouldings was produced by profiling the resin temperature during injection to alter the cure sequence. A benchmark moulding, representing conventional RTM, was made by injecting polyester resin [Synolac 6345 initiated with 2% acetyl acetone peroxide (Trigonox 44B) and 0.5% cobalt accelerator (NL49P)] at ambient temperature (24°C) into a mould heated to 40°C. Four additional mouldings were produced by ramping the resin temperature as follows: 40-45°C, 40-50°C, 40-55°C, and 40-60°C. The preheating sequence was based upon a linear ramping of the resin set point temperature as a function of the total mass of resin injected. The set point temperature was initialised to 40°C at the start of injection (0 kg injected), and increased to the maximum temperature by the end of injection (9 kg injected). Applying a temperature ramp from 40-50°C led to coincident resin cure across the mould surface with a 36% reduction in cycle time compared to the moulding produced by conventional RTM. This situation represented the minimum cycle time possible for the given moulding conditions.

Figure 2 shows that the pressure within the mould cavity during cure increased along the diagonal from the mould periphery to the injection gate for mouldings produced by conventional RTM (resin temperatures of 22°C and 24°C). This high pressure, termed the pre-exotherm pressure, was identified by Kendall [9] as a characteristic of centre gate injection. Resin cured first at the mould periphery creating a rigid seal, entrapping a pool of uncured resin within the mould. The resin temperature increased through mould heating and the exothermic cure reaction. As a result, thermal expansion of the resin occurred, generating a pressure that was transmitted into the liquid pool. Compression within the liquid pool increased as the cure front advanced inward, generating a consecutively higher pre-exotherm pressure. Thus, the intensity of the pre-exotherm pressure was greatest at the injection gate. Kendall [9] recorded pre-exotherm pressures five times greater than the injection pressure, concluding that they were an important consideration in mould design. Constant temperature resin injection had no effect on the cure sequence so that high pre-exotherm pressures were measured at all elevated resin temperatures. Ramping the resin temperature to promote coincident cure reduced this pre-

exotherm pressure to the hydrostatic level as no entrapment of the pool occurred. This suggested that mould deflections were reduced during the cure phase.

THICKNESS VARIATIONS IN RTM LAMINATES

High pre-exotherm pressure could lead to damage in moulds not designed to prevent pressure induced deflections. In addition, these deflections could result in part thickness variations. Kendall [9] produced a series of plaque mouldings with pre-exotherm pressures ranging from 0 bar to 28 bar. The thickness of the laminate increased by an average of 10% at 28 bar leading to the conclusion that high pre-exotherm pressures influenced component quality appreciably.

A study was performed to determine whether high pre-exotherm pressures at the injection gate affected the thickness of the undershield component. Disks (19 mm in diameter) were cut from four laminates near the mould periphery and the injection gate. Two mouldings (Numbers 5454 and 5456) exhibited a typical cure sequence from the periphery to the centre of the mould and had high pre-exotherm pressures at the injection gate (between 17 bar and 25 bar). The other two mouldings (Numbers 5437 and 5435) were produced using a coincident cure sequence and exhibited low pre-exotherm pressures at the injection gate (approximately 1 bar). Variation in thickness of the disks between the mould periphery and injection gate was determined with the results being presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The thickness across the mouldings with a high pre-exotherm pressure (Table 1) increased on average by 8.8% from the mould periphery to the injection gate. The average increase was reduced substantially to 4.1% for mouldings produced with a low pre-exotherm pressure (Table 2). These results confirmed the findings by Kendall, and suggested that component quality is related directly to the pre-exotherm pressure.

Table 1: Variation in Laminate Thickness for Mouldings with a Maximum Pre-Exotherm Pressure of 25 Bar

Reference No.	Moulding Thickness		Thickness Increase(%)
	Periphery	Gate	
5456	7.84	8.51	8.5
5454	7.48	8.16	9.1
Average Values	7.66	8.34	8.8

Table 2: Variation in Laminate Thickness for Mouldings with a Maximum Pre-Exotherm Pressure of 2 Bar

Reference No.	Moulding Thickness		Thickness Increase(%)
	Periphery	Gate	
5437	9.26	9.59	3.6
5435	9.10	9.51	4.5
Average Values	9.18	9.55	4.1

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF RTM LAMINATES

Rudd and Revill [10] demonstrated that the tensile properties of RTM laminates were sensitive to cycle time. Decreasing the cycle time reduced the period available for fibre wet-out, prompting a decrease in the tensile modulus and strength of continuous filament random mat (CFRM) laminates. Reducing the resin viscosity was expected to promote better flow through the

preform and enhance fibre wet-out, for improved tensile properties. Hayward and Harris [11] showed that lowering resin viscosity by increasing the mould temperature produced no difference in the shear strength or modulus of moulded components.

Five laminates were produced by injecting polyester resin [Synolac 6345 initiated with 2% bis t-butyl peroxy dicarbonate (Perkadox 16)] at 22°C, 30°C, 40°C, 45°C and 50°C into a mould heated to 60°C. A CFRM reinforcement was used resulting in a fibre volume fraction of 16%. Seven specimens were cut from each undershield (250 mm × 25 mm × 6 mm) along the weft direction of the glass mat as shown in Figure 3. The tensile modulus (E) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the specimens were measured. The laminates were tested to BS 2782:Part 10:Method 1003 on an Instron Universal Mechanical Tester Model 1195 having a 100 kN load cell. Longitudinal displacements were recorded by an extensometer at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min.

Figure 4a shows the variation in modulus as a function of the resin preheat temperature. Average modulus values ranged from 5.5 GPa to 7.0 GPa, although no statistically significant difference was measured. Figure 4b shows similar results for the laminate tensile strength as a function of resin preheat temperature. Variation in average strength values were negligible ranging from 112 MPa at 40°C and 126 MPa at 22°C. These results suggested that preheating the resin to a constant temperature during injection did not affect the tensile properties of RTM laminates appreciably.

Analysis of tensile properties provided information on the overall effect of resin preheating on fibre reinforced laminates. However, further investigation was necessary to determine its effect on the resin system.

DEGREE OF CURE MEASUREMENTS BY GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY

Compared to resin injected at ambient temperature, resin injected at a constant elevated temperature experiences a different thermal history. As a result, the properties of the matrix could be altered. Preheated resin would be nearer to its activation temperature at the end of injection, so that the polymerisation reaction may be initiated preferentially, resulting in a more highly crosslinked structure. Tensile tests on the laminates did not confirm this hypothesis. However, the strength of the fibre reinforcement, and the fibre to matrix interface was expected to dominate these results. A measurement of the degree of cure was necessary to understand fully the effect of resin preheating on the matrix.

Experimental Procedure for Degree of Cure Measurements Using Gas Chromatography

A polyester resin consists of an unsaturated resin molecule dissolved in a styrene monomer to form a homogeneous solution. Curing involves copolymerisation of the styrene and unsaturated resin. In principle, copolymerisation will cease automatically when all the styrene has reacted [12]. Based upon the homogeneous nature of the resin, it is convenient to define the fully cured state as having 0% residual styrene and the uncured state as having 100% residual styrene. The amount of residual styrene in the polyester resin can be measured by gas chromatography.

Residual styrene content measurements were made on two laminates produced by constant temperature resin injection at 20°C and 50°C in a mould heated to 60°C. Glass fibre blanks were removed from the preform at eight locations along the mould diagonal before injection to form pure resin samples at those locations. Resin disks (19 mm diameter) were cut from the laminate

directly after demoulding. The samples were prepared for gas chromatography testing according to a modified version of BS 2782:Part 4:Method 453A. A Perkin-Elmer 8500 Gas Chromatograph was used to measure residual styrene content in the samples.

Results of the Degree of Cure Measurements Using Gas Chromatography

The amount of residual styrene at locations along the mould diagonal (positions 2-5) is shown in Figure 5. Insignificant variations in residual styrene levels were measured between the two mouldings. The majority of the laminates (positions 2-4) were cured to approximately 93%. A higher degree of cure (97%) was measured at the injection gate for both laminates. The reason for a higher degree of cure at the injection gate was not clear, however, Huang et al. [13] have suggested that increased pressure could increase the overall degree of cure. This explanation would be compatible with the higher cure pressures occurring near the injection gate as shown in Figure 2 for conventional RTM.

The results shown in Figure 5 demonstrate that resin preheating had no significant effect on the degree of cure for RTM laminates. Figure 6 provides further evidence to support this claim. Preheating the resin to 50°C reduced the amount of thermal quench at the injection gate compared to the moulding produced with resin at 22°C. However, the similarity in shape of the thermal histories above the mould temperature (60°C) suggests that the cure reaction proceeded at the same rate for both mouldings.

CONCLUSIONS

Use of an in-line microwave resin preheating system reduced RTM production cycle times by compensating for thermal quench at the injection gate. Profiling of the resin preheat temperature reduced localised in-mould pressures during the cure phase, and decreased mould deflections. As a result, the variation in the component thickness along the length of the component decreased by more than 50%. Furthermore, this suggested that lighter and more thermally responsive shell moulds could be employed.

Resin preheated to a constant temperature during injection had an insignificant effect on the tensile properties of RTM laminates. Tensile tests on laminates produced at a series of resin temperatures showed an insignificant effect on the modulus and strength. This implied that preheating the resin to lower its viscosity did not improve fibre wet-out. However, since impregnation times were reduced, this suggested that the equivalent fibre wet-out had occurred over a shorter interval. These results indicate that resin preheating could be used to reduce cycle times without lowering the structural integrity of RTM components.

Preheating resin was determined to have no effect on the degree of cure for the laminates. This suggested that while resin preheating altered the thermal history of the resin, it did not change the kinetics of the cure reaction.

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Figure 1: Schematic of the RTM Facility

Figure 2: Effect of ramped resin temperature injection on the peak pre-exotherm pressures across the undershield mould

Figure 3: Orientation of tensile test specimens on the undershield component

Figure 4a: Average modulus values for RTM laminates

Figure 4b: Average UTS values for RTM laminates

Figure 5: Degree of cure along undershield moulding produced with resin injected at 20C and 50C

Figure 6: Thermal histories at the injection gate (position 5) demonstrating the similarities in resin cure kinetics between mouldings made with and without resin preheating